

Project Deliverable D-JRP17- WP 6.Del 1

Workpackage 6

Responsible Partner: APHA

Contributing partners: ANSES, FLI, ISZAM,
WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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DELIVERABLE REPORT D-JRP17-WP6.DEL1: REVIEW OF TOOLKITS FOR INFECTIOUS DISEASES

Description of the task

The toolkit will aim to improve accessibility to credible and up-to-date information on emerging *Brucella* threats of public health significance in a 'one-stop' format that is quick and easy to use. The task will take all the necessary information generated by other IDEMBRU WPs and will make use of the deliverables produced during the project. The work package will be split in two main tasks:

This task assessed currently available toolkits for other pathogens in order to identify strengths and weaknesses from previous experiences. Tools available at European Union level for early detection of, and response to, multi-country foodborne events (Epidemic Intelligence and Information System for food- and waterborne diseases (EPIS-FWD), Early Warning and Response System (EWRS) platform, Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) platform and the Food Chain-Lab tool) will be reviewed as existing approaches.

Currently available toolkits have been assessed for other pathogens in order to identify strengths and weaknesses from previous experiences. Tools available at European Union level for early detection of, and response to, multi-country foodborne events (Epidemic Intelligence and Information System for food- and waterborne diseases (EPIS-FWD), Early Warning and Response System (EWRS) platform, Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) platform and the Food Chain-Lab tool) have been reviewed as existing approaches. After presented analyses, the leaders and deputies of all WPs have considered the WHO "Monkeypox Outbreak Toolbox" as the best reflecting the organization of a toolkit for emerging *Brucella* species, to fulfil the scope of the project. The resource has then taken into consideration for the development of the toolbox; it is available on the following web address:

<https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/monkeypox-outbreak-toolbox>